

MANAGING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS: STRATEGIES FOR CHATGPT.

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Abstract. The integration of ChatGPT in educational settings is revolutionizing teaching methodologies, offering personalized feedback and interactive learning experiences, while also posing challenges such as potential for academic dishonesty and diminished critical thinking skills. The paper examines the theoretical underpinnings and methodological consequences of academic research on artificial intelligence (AI) technologies in everyday life. The paper provides a functional definition of AI and asserts that AI should be analyzed in conjunction with artificial sociality. The article explores the capacity of AI to address contemporary challenges in educational setting. The study argues that the difficulties presented by AI technologies and its possible solutions.

Keywords: ChatGPT, critical thinking skills, artificial intelligence, technologies teaching methodologies

Annotatsiya. Chatgpt-ning ta'limni tashkil etish jarayoniga individuallashtirilgan fikr-mulohazalar va interaktiv o'quv tajribalarini taklif qilish, shuningdek, akademik nohaqlik va tanqidiy fikrlash qobiliyatlarini pasaytirish kabi muammolarni keltirib chiqarish orqali o'qitish metodologiyasini ta'sir qiladi qiladi. Maqolada sun'iy intellekt (SI) texnologiyalari bo'yicha ilmiy tadqiqotlarning nazariy asoslari va uslubiy oqibatlari kundalik hayotga solishtirilgan holda ko'rib chiqiladi. Maqolada sun'iy intellektning ta'rifi hamda uning sun'iy jamiyat bilan birgalikda tahlil qilish kerakligi ta'kidlangan. Shuningdek, sun'iy intellektning ta'lim muhitidagi zamonaviy muammolarni hal qilish qobiliyati o'rganiladi. Tadqiqot SI texnologiyalari natijasida duch kelinadigan qiyinchiliklar va ularning amaliy echimlari taklif etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ChatGPT, tanqidiy fikrlash qobiliyatlari, sun'iy intellekt, texnologiyani o'rganish metodologiyalari

Аннотация. Интеграция ChatGPT в образовательные настройки революционизирует методологии преподавания, предлагая персонализированную обратную связь и интерактивные учебные опыты, а также создавая проблемы, такие как потенциал для академической нечестности и снижения навыков критического мышления. В статье рассматриваются теоретические основы и методологические последствия научных исследований в области технологий искусственного интеллекта (ИИ) в повседневной жизни. В статье содержится функциональное определение искусственного интеллекта и утверждается, что искусственный интеллект должен анализироваться в сочетании с искусственной социальностью. В статье исследуется способность ИИ решать современные проблемы в образовательной среде. В исследовании утверждается, что трудности, с которыми сталкиваются технологии ИИ и их возможные решения.

Ключевые слова: ChatGPT, навыки критического мышления, искусственный интеллект, методологии обучения технологиям

Managing Artificial Intelligence in educational institutions, particularly strategies for ChatGPT, involves leveraging its benefits while addressing potential challenges. ChatGPT can support event planning in classes, enhance programming learning, improve administrative tasks,

and boost writing skills in students [1] [2] [3] [4]. However, concerns exist regarding cheating, diminished critical thinking, and plagiarism risks associated with its use [5]. To effectively manage ChatGPT, institutions can focus on educating students and faculty about its proper use, integrating it into teaching methods for enhanced learning experiences, and implementing measures to ensure academic integrity and originality in student work. By embracing ChatGPT as a valuable tool while addressing its challenges through appropriate policies and guidelines, educational institutions can harness its potential to enrich the learning environment effectively.

AI is also being used in classrooms. Adaptive learning is one type of AI used in some edtech, while facial recognition is another. Though generative AI is still in its infancy, particularly in educational settings, it already produces writing tools that can compose entire essays in response to a brief prompt (such as ChatGPT and Bard). Although we frequently encounter predictive text in text messages or Google Docs, it's somewhat unusual to have a program generate a full text based on straightforward inquiries or commands. Even if it isn't very sophisticated yet when it comes to producing truly original content, many instructors are nonetheless concerned about it.

Present Issues

It makes sense that as technology advances and grows more complex, we would be concerned about both present and future difficulties. Here are a few recent worries:

Misuses

Images, movies, and audio files that appear or sound like someone you know—a celebrity, a public figure, or even a family member—are known as deepfakes. This can even apply to pornographic films or photos that were created without permission using AI. As it stands, children are already creating nude pictures of their classmates with "nudifying" applications.

Misinformation and biases

Since artificial intelligence can only learn from its source(s), it absorbs the prejudices, false facts, and problematic content of the original content. Furthermore, as facial recognition has shown, unconscious bias will almost certainly be ingrained into the tool's architecture if the development team isn't representative.

Ethics

The content generated by AI tools is a blend of many other people's works, and artists are frequently not given consistent or full credit because these programs scrape content from a wide range of sources. Additionally, the topic of data privacy in relation to generative AI is complex and multifaceted.

The act of copying

Plagiarism is one of instructors' main concerns. Students are already turning in essays produced by AI as their own.

Strategies for Addressing Concerns

Given the multitude of concerns and lack of clarity, it is not surprising that some instructors feel overwhelmed by the entire concept. However, it is advisable to avoid feeling panicked. There are actions we can do and assets we can utilize.

Strategies for Dealing with Abuses

Preempt possible issues by promoting AI knowledge and engaging in conversations regarding the technology's detrimental uses. Inform students about the existence of deepfakes on the internet, emphasizing the importance of maintaining a critical attitude towards particularly alarming or extensively shared audio and video content to avoid being manipulated emotionally. Although certain defects can still be observed, they are becoming increasingly challenging to

discern. Discuss the concept of consent in relation to content. Prior to using an AI tool to process someone's image, it is crucial to obtain their explicit consent, just as one would seek permission before capturing a photograph or video. Promote children's empathy by inquiring about their potential emotions if someone were to publish anything humiliating about them.

Ensure a comprehensive understanding of the repercussions associated with utilizing artificial intelligence to produce explicit imagery. Inform students that they may encounter advertisements on platforms such as TikTok promoting applications for generating explicit images. While some may exhibit curiosity or find it amusing (because to the non-authentic nature of the images), employing artificial intelligence to produce explicit photographs of an individual constitutes harassment and is highly likely to be deemed criminal. Not only does it cause injury to the victim, but it could also result in law enforcement intervention.

Strategies for Managing Biases and Misinformation

Present students with AI-generated visuals that correspond to specified prompts and engage in a discussion on the biases depicted in the resulting output. Utilize various forms of media, such as science fiction movies, television shows, and books, to initiate conversations around algorithmic prejudice, the deficiencies of facial recognition technology, and other related topics. Ensure that students are reminded to incorporate requests for source links when utilizing artificial intelligence for research purposes. (Certain tools may provide hyperlinks to their source material upon request.) Instruct pupils to verify each hyperlink.

Inform students about the phenomenon of AI hallucinations. AI can amalgamate information from its data sets in order to create entirely fabricated content. AI technologies can also assert to experience emotions such as love, perceive different human senses, and do other functions. It is crucial for pupils, particularly younger ones, to comprehend that an AI chatbot may mimic a human being, but it is intentionally created by actual individuals.

How to Manage the Ethical Considerations

Discuss the questionable ethical aspects of generative AI and delve into a broader conversation about the consequences of technology advancements and the appropriate approaches to managing them. Discuss the current disparity in access to digital technology and the implications of upcoming advancements for individuals who lack the financial means to acquire it. What are the consequences when tools like these begin to incur charges for additional features? Examine the safeguarding of intellectual property. Which precautionary measures should we do to proactively address potential issues? Discuss the topic of data privacy. What data does AI now acquire, and what data could it potentially acquire in the future? How does it utilize the information provided? Discuss the potential ramifications of an artificial intelligence that can compile information about you from various web sources.

Strategies for Dealing with Plagiarism

Engage in hands-on experimentation with AI systems to gain a comprehensive understanding of their capabilities and limitations. Connect your prompts and evaluate them. Familiarize oneself with pupils' fully writing. Engage in classroom writing activities while being cognizant of certain students' constraints in participating. Use formative assessment to obtain periodic snapshots of progress across a span of time. Assess your prompts and strive to incorporate a student-centered strategy that emphasizes emotional intelligence and prior knowledge. According to a teacher, if you want specific answers, avoid asking general inquiries. Conduct a collaborative evaluation of AI technologies and engage in a discussion regarding their constraints. Incorporate a covert term or phrase in your assignment that remains hidden from the student. This

keyword can be utilized later to determine if the student has copied the prompt into an artificial intelligence program.

As a final option, there are technologies available for detecting artificial intelligence (AI), although it is important to note that these techniques are not flawless and often incorrectly identify plagiarism roughly 50% of the time. ChatGPT and similar programs lack the capacity to establish emotional bonds with readers.

Implications for the Future

Due to the relentless pace of technological advancement, we are unable to sufficiently contemplate and prepare for all of its consequences. However, we can engage students in examining this uncertainty.

Escalating concerns over privacy. Furthermore, our understanding of the full extent of AI's effects on privacy remains incomplete. One important lesson we have learned is that data is really valuable. In addition, due to the constant learning capabilities of AI, any personal information we provide is potentially susceptible to being accessed by others. Shifts in employment marketplaces and the required competencies. Ultimately, the extent to which AI will transform the job economy remains speculative. Equipping pupils for a future that surpasses our current imagination is a genuine task.

Strategies for Addressing Future Considerations

Embrace a futuristic mindset: Inquire with students about the impact of AI on the employment market and the skills they anticipate will be necessary.

Design a project-oriented task that enables students to conduct study on this technology that will undeniably influence their lives. Discuss the appropriate legislation and policies that should be implemented by the government for the field of artificial intelligence (AI).

ChatGPT's integration into educational settings has demonstrated significant potential in enhancing learning experiences and administrative efficiency, though it also introduces challenges related to academic integrity and security concerns. The technology's ability to support creative writing and problem-solving skills underscores its value as an educational tool, necessitating further exploration into its pedagogical applications. Despite its benefits, the need for critical evaluation of ChatGPT-generated content and the development of strategies to mitigate its limitations are paramount for its responsible use in academia. As ChatGPT continues to evolve, ongoing research and adaptation of policies will be crucial in harnessing its capabilities while safeguarding the educational values of originality and critical thinking.

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